

Challenges met during the design of floating structures in the North Sea and the Barents Sea.

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Abstract. For the design of floating structures in the North Sea and the Barents Sea, several challenges are met because of the harsh climate conditions of these seas. Due to hard soil conditions in the North Sea, piling represented a challenge for the design of steel production units for oil and gas, and large concrete support structures were designed, fabricated, and installed. These structures are in the fabrication and installation phases in floating conditions, and strength and stability considerations must be satisfied. Furthermore, the wave climate represents higher fatigue damage than, for example, in the Gulf of Mexico. The drilling rigs have to be designed for extreme in-place conditions, and intact stability is an issue when the weight of the drilling equipment and mud is as large as possible. Also, waves in the deck structure have been of concern with the loss of personnel due to wave impact on the living quarters. In one case, the weight of the topsides exceeded the intact stability criteria, and additional buoyancy tanks had to be added. The Floating production units (FPSOs) are on standby in harsh weather, and fatigue is of higher concern than for ships encountering many different types of sea states. The FPSOs are oriented against the wave direction to limit roll motions; however, when crossing seas, the ships could get into roll resonance with the long swell waves. The Barents Sea gives rise to challenges due to the high probability of sea spray icing and sudden polar low pressures, causing long weather downtime. The learning from designing floating structures for these seas represents a valuable contribution to the design basis for new floating structures in harsh environments.

Keywords: *Concrete platforms in temporary phases, Intact stability of drilling rigs, Waves in the deck, FPSO motion characteristics, Sea spray icing.*

1 Introduction

The learnings from failures in projects are normally not systematic, except for very large failures/disasters causing loss of many lives (like the Piper Alpha accident [1] in the UK sector of the North Sea or the loss of Alexander Kielland semisubmersible platform [2] in the Southern North Sea), disasters causing large pollution (like the Macondo well blow out and the loss of Deepwater Horizon drilling platform [3] in the Gulf of Mexico) or disasters causing considerable loss of assets (like the loss of the concrete gravity platform Sleipner A [4] under construction in a Norwegian fjord). Although special investigations are conducted in large-scale disasters, a systematic analysis of common effects causing failures or near failures is not available.

For less serious incidents, local or company investigations are undertaken, limiting the information and possibility for learning to a small group of persons/ companies. In the case of near misses, there is no systematic collection of information, and learning is not widespread. This could, potentially, be improved if the insurance industry demanded better background information and risk analysis before accepting insurance coverage.

Governments could also call for a thorough investigation regime, like in aviation, where all investigation reports from large accidents are disseminated widely.

A reminder of incidents causing accidents or challenges is in place, and this paper focuses on floating structures in the North Sea and the Barents Sea. The objective is to share information about types of failures for those involved in new projects and to initiate the acquisition of a database of challenges that may appear during the design, construction, transport, installation, and operation of large offshore structures. The discussion will mainly be related to technical aspects, although many of the challenges are rooted in human mistakes or failures, and even in a lack of knowledge.

2 Experience from offshore floating units being fabricated in concrete.

Support structures for oil and gas production are traditionally fabricated from steel. With the development of North Sea oil and gas fields, the feasibility of steel structures was challenged due to the harsh physical environmental conditions, causing fatigue damage to the joints, and due to hard soils, causing piling to be challenging. Several operators, therefore, selected gravity-based structures made from concrete to mitigate these

concerns. Among these companies were Shell, Esso, Mobil, BP, and Statoil. During the fabrication and installation phases, these structures are in a floating mode. While the dimensions of steel structures typically are one to two inches, concrete structures must have wall thicknesses in the order of several decimeters to withstand the hydrostatic pressure. However, as concrete is very weak to withstand tension forces, prestressing is required to ensure structural capacity where tension forces are present. Furthermore, the inner and outer layers of reinforcement in a wall must be linked together with stirrups to avoid splitting of the concrete wall. Another concern is corrosion of rebars in the offshore environment, which is solved by using very dense and vibrated concrete. The concrete structures installed in the North Sea are, in general, in very good structural condition, even after 50 years in service.

However, during the fabrication phases, challenges were large for some of these structures. Some examples will be discussed. The concrete gravity platform Statfjord A (for 145m water depth) was installed on the seafloor in 1976 after having survived cracks during tow out to the location because of insufficient reinforcement in a critical joint where the buoyancy cells are connected. The learning was brought back to later designs; however, the concrete platform Sleipner A (for 82 m water depth) was not properly designed for the external pressure, and experienced overload and collapse during deepwater testing on 23 August 1991 in a Norwegian Fjord [4]. The failure was attributed to overreliance on the Finite Element Analysis, where inappropriate finite elements were used; thus, critical joints between the cylindrical buoyancy cells (Figure 1) did not have sufficient reinforcement (underestimation by 47%). The FEA was carried out with a program (Nastran) unfamiliar to the project team, and the project personnel lacked the experience to identify the lack of necessary reinforcement and the connection between the inner and outer reinforcement in a concrete joint [5]. An evaluation of the relevant Management of Resource Constraints and System Safety was carried out [6].

Figure 1. Critical joint of Sleipner A where the cracks occurred.

The loss of the Sleipner A platform caused an investigation of other platforms under construction. The Draugen monotower platform (for 251m water depth) was checked for an appropriate connection between the inner and outer reinforcement of the walls. The concern was related to possible water ingress from ballast piping that potentially could split the concrete walls during submergence when transferring the deck over the top of the platform. Furthermore, the tower has a diameter in the waterline (15m) widening out at the top to form a flat-sided cube. This geometry could cause the platform to have large “ringing-type” vibrations in large waves [7]. No large issues were detected; however, the amount of reinforcement at the bottom of the shaft (where the wall thickness is more than 2m) was increased.

The large Troll A platform under construction (for 303 m water depth) was also checked for the effects of ringing, and the amount of reinforcement had to be increased. Another effect was detected at the bottom of the utility shaft of the platform. This shaft is empty, accommodating all risers and ballast systems. The ballast piping was cast in large concrete blocks near the bottom of the shaft. When the outer pressure during deck transfer acts on the 2 m-thick concrete walls, the walls will have some deformations. Where the concrete blocks with the ballast piping are encapsulated, the deformation will be less. At the transition between the wall and the wall with the concrete blocks attached, there will be a sharp gradient in the deformation. This would not be a problem for normal ductile steel ballast piping; however, the ballast piping used was made from GRVE composite material, allowing no shear forces. A warning was raised [8] to ensure the ballast piping was closed during the entire construction period to avoid a breakage of this piping with an influx of water, potentially splitting the concrete wall (Figure 2), [9]. The cost related to mitigating the seemingly insignificant failure became quite high (in the order of several hundred million NOK). Note that the Draugen and the Troll platforms are supported by very long cells (8m and 30m, respectively) penetrating the soft sea bottom to reach a harder layer for safe foundation.

Figure 2. Section of the lower dome of the Troll A concrete platform showing GRVE pipes and protective coating [8].

Two floating concrete platforms are placed on the Norwegian Continental Shelf: the Troll B Semisubmersible platform and the Heidun TLP (for 350m water depth). The Heidun TLP has 4 large columns, where two are connected by concrete beams to support the deck. During detailed engineering, it was detected that waves coming in from an angle with the beams give rise to torsion forces in the modules fixed to the beams. The modules had, therefore, to be considerably strengthened to allow for these torsional forces.

This summarizes some challenges (and failures) related to the use of concrete in the offshore environment. Despite the problems encountered, no life was lost, and no environmental pollution was spread in the case of the above-mentioned projects. The possibility of incorporating mitigating measures also shows that concrete is a material that is fully feasible for use with offshore floating units. A risk analysis of the construction project is, however, strongly recommended [10].

A full identification of all hazards during towing and placing the Troll A at the offshore site was carried out, limiting the weather to good forecasts during the tow. Such a risk analysis was also conducted for the transport of the process modules (for an LNG plant) from the fabrication yard in Cadiz (Spain) to Melkøya (near Hammerfest, Norway). The process module was placed on a concrete barge that was to be towed into a dock at the site. The use of a concrete barge to transport the process module was decided to avoid large construction work in the bitterly cold Arctic weather in the north of Norway. The concrete barge and the process equipment were transferred onto *Mighty Servant* (a heavy transport vessel) for the transport from Spain to Northern Norway. The risk analysis set strict limitations on weather forecasts along the towing route and identified safe harbors for shelter in case of poor weather forecasts.

3. Semisubmersible units

Drilling rigs must be designed for extreme in-place conditions and intact stability. This is challenging, as it is required to have the maximum weight of drilling equipment and mud onboard to reduce the required supply services. This is of particular importance in the Barents Sea as the weather during the winter can be harsh for long periods, and sea spray icing can be of concern. The logistics of supply services are, therefore, challenging situations, and delays could occur.

The rigs must be designed and operated with sufficiently long columns to avoid the deck dipping into the water in large waves. A recent situation with the loss of a person in December 2015 was due to unexpected, steep waves (rogue waves) interacting with the living quarters on a drilling rig [11]. The new design was not properly tested and analyzed for North Sea conditions.

A special case of challenging stability was met when a semisubmersible production unit was selected for a gas/condensate field on Haltenbanken, offshore Central Norway. The design was well established, and to have a maximum of production equipment installed on the unit, the living quarters were to be fabricated from aluminum to save weight. A lack of communication between the engineering and procurement groups in the project led to the selection of the less costly steel option. Consequently, the rig design had to be upgraded with larger buoyancy volumes and an increased anchor system to handle the larger floater. The field came into production in 2005. Buying cheaply is, however, not always the best option.

The drilling rig *Alexander Kielland* was used as a living quarters unit on the Ekofisk field in the southern North Sea. The pentagon-type unit had strict requirements for the anchor pattern; however, the anchor system was changed for this special assignment due to congestion of platforms at the Ekofisk field. A failure in one of the legs

caused initial fatigue damage to develop, and eventually, one of the five legs broke off. As work was ongoing in the pontoons, safety doors were open with cables protruding through the doors, and the platform took in water and capsized (Figure 3) shortly after on 27 March 1980, killing 123 people [2].

Figure 3. The Alexander Kielland capsizes [2].

10 days after the tragic loss of the Alexander Kielland platform, the sister platform, Henrik Ibsen, was at the key side in Tananger Harbor near Stavanger. A ballast valve was accidentally opened, and the platform was set down on the seafloor, thereby avoiding capsizing. This failure was entirely due to human failure; however, it could have been fatal for people onboard if the water depth at the key side had been deeper, causing a larger heel angle of the platform with a large living quarter, see Figure 4.

Figure 4. The semi-submersible Henrik Ibsen at the key side in Tananger, Norway (Courtesy The Norwegian Petroleum Museum).

Internationally, the loss of the drilling platform Ocean Ranger offshore Newfoundland, where a large wave damaged a window, allowing water to enter the rig and ultimately sink on 15 February 1982 with 84 persons onboard, also reminds us of the need to ensure stability and prevent water ingress into a semisubmersible unit.

Further, the loss of Petrobras 36 (P-36), a floating semi-submersible oil production platform, should be mentioned. The platform sank on 20 March 2001, after an explosion in one of the columns ripped open a water intake pipe, and it was not possible to repair the damage. During the explosion, there were 11 fatalities. The causes of the failure should be relevant for all projects [12]:

- Poor design and placement of key safety-critical parts
- Component failure without sufficient backups
- Lack of training and communication
- Focus on cost-cutting

The largest disaster concerning pollution is associated with the blowout of the Macondo well in the Gulf of Mexico [3]. The Deepwater Horizon drilling rig exploded and sank on 22 April 2010. 11 crewmen were lost. The oil that was spilled during the 87 days until the well was capped is estimated to be 4 million barrels. The drilling rig was operated incorrectly in this incident, with too little attention to safety barriers in the well. The rig by itself could not have been saved if it had been built with more attention to structural safety, because of the large explosion.

4. Floating production units (FSOs and FPSOs)

The Floating Storage and Offloading Units (FSOs) and Floating Production, Storage, and Offloading Units (FPSOs) are on standby in harsh weather. The vessels will turn toward the waves to limit roll motions, which is challenging for the processing equipment. In areas with a dominant wave direction, these vessels will be more exposed to fatigue damage compared to vessels encountering waves from many directions, such as ocean-going vessels. This became of concern for the Norne FPSO located on the Haltenbanken off mid-Norway. Fatigue tests were carried out for the steel plate, and eventually, the vessel was confirmed to be safe [13]. A similar concern was raised for the Johan Castberg FPSO installed recently, 240 km north of the Norwegian coast in the Barents Sea. The bow of the vessel under construction had to be modified to ensure sufficient fatigue life (Fig. 5). The hook-up period took a long time, as the weather conditions throughout the winter of 2024 to 2025 were harsh, with several polar low pressures (local hurricanes) passing the vessel. The operator had to wait for suitable weather for installation work, and the start-up of the oil production was somewhat delayed.

Figure 5. The Johan Castberg FPSO is anchored at the field 240 km north of the Norwegian Coast in the Barents Sea. (Courtesy Equinor).

Although the FSOs and the FPSOs are oriented against the wave direction to limit roll motions, the ships could get into roll resonance with the long swell waves in the case of crossing seas. This will happen during a situation with wind waves combined with an approaching low-pressure pressure where long swell waves are preceding the shorter waves. As the low pressures from the Atlantic approach from the southwesterly direction, such situations are expected to occur along the Norwegian Coast in the Norwegian Sea and the Barents Sea. The situation at the Norne field described in [14] was unexpected and caused considerable concern, as the process cannot be handled in a vessel roll situation. Note that the processing equipment is installed across the vessel and cannot be operated when there is a large roll motion.

In the North Sea, it is customary for the waves to wash over the deck of the FPSOs; we have a “green water loading” situation. The situation is well known for ships in harsh weather [15]. In January 2000, green water hit the living quarters on the bow of the Varg FPSO, damaging a window on the second floor and flooding the area behind it. The vessel was designed for green water loading, but a weak arrangement of the window resulted in damage. Potentially, the incident could have resulted in serious damage to critical equipment and progressive water filling of the bow part of the FPSO.

The Barents Sea gives rise to challenges due to the high probability of sea spray icing, in particular in situations of sudden polar low pressures causing long weather downtime [16]. Large and wide vessels are stable with a considerable amount of sea spray icing; however, smaller vessels with considerable construction equipment mounted could be in danger, as the ice will have a high center of gravity, causing loss of metacenter stability of the vessel. Fishing vessels are particularly exposed to sea spray icing due to the large amounts of equipment onboard. Numerous fishing vessels have sunk due to loss of intact stability caused by sea spray icing. The

phenomenon is well known in cold climates, even south of the North Sea, when sudden harsh weather with strong winds and large waves occurs [17].

The learning from designing floating structures for these cold climate seas represents a valuable contribution to the design basis for new floating structures in harsh environments.

5. Recommendations based on lessons learnt

All publicly available information about safe design and operations should be openly shared.

The Norwegian Ocean Industry Authority's (Havtil) regulatory authority covers the whole of the Norwegian continental shelf (NCS) and seven petroleum-related plants on land. Offshore renewable energy production and CO₂ management are also included. Maritime activities are overseen by the Norwegian Maritime Authority. Audit and Investigation reports prepared by Havtil are published on their homepage, <https://www.havtil.no/en/>. Occasionally, Havtil presents information about failures at international conferences, see e.g. [18]. However, this important information is hidden behind payment walls and is not available to engineers who would benefit from reading this summary. A retired chief engineer of Havtil, on the other hand, posted all published information on the net [19]. However, near misses or design failures in the early phases of projects will not necessarily be reported to the authorities. In conclusion, there would be a need for easier sharing of information. This might be achieved by letting the library of the actual authority release the paper to those requesting a copy.

Buoyancy during operations is critical and must be ensured through hazard and operational analysis (Hazids). Of particular concern are systems to ensure that all openings to the sea are closed.

Many of the lessons learnt from failures related to floating offshore structures relate to a lack of awareness of buoyancy and water pressure. Concrete floating structures are particularly vulnerable, as the steel bar reinforcement is the main structural element. Semi-submersible floating units made from steel are divided into independent compartments, and stability is granted in case of the integrity and tightness of a certain number of compartments. However, in many situations, tightness and full compartment isolation are not granted as doors dividing compartments are kept open for easy access, as in the case of ongoing maintenance.

Compartments must be independent, and the designer must consider worst-case scenarios. During operations, compartments must always be functional.

Information about failures related to vessels for production or storage is needed, as many offshore fields are developed by vessels. Compartmentation has been an issue since the loss of the Titanic; however, ships are still built without proper compartmentation. A lesson for the offshore industry can be learned from the sinking of the Norwegian Frigate Helge Ingstad. The vessel was set on a shoal to avoid sinking after a collision, as the piping between the "watertight compartments" was routed in openings between the compartments [20].

Information from past challenges must be shared and used to conduct hazard analysis.

The recommendation is to ensure that information from past challenges and incidents is shared. With this information available, it will be easier to conduct hazard identification assessments, Hazids. This risk assessment tool is very strong in case a group of experienced engineers comes together for the identification of hazards. Furthermore, the Hazids must be followed by an operational hazard analysis, a Hazop. These tools are part of a construction phase risk analysis that should be considered for offshore projects [10]. An important part of a construction risk analysis is to ensure that sufficient robustness is incorporated in the design, through appropriate redundancy in critical elements and operations. Some companies arrange for independent reviews of projects throughout the different project phases. Experienced personnel are involved in these reviews. This was the case for the development of the Troll gas project in the 1980s. The success of the Troll gas development project has ensured gas delivery to Europe from the Norwegian shelf for many decades.

Close cooperation between all parties involved is important.

In this paper, the role of the parties involved in a project is discussed. These are the field operator, the designer, the construction companies, the installation contractor, and the operating personnel. The role of the authorities is emphasized, requesting easy-to-read information about concerns and reports that have been prepared.

Another group that should be involved in the risk assessment is the insurers. In the case of a failure, the insurance company will have to pay out large sums. Could insurance companies set tougher requirements to accept and undertake insurance? Has the technical optimization gone too far, limiting the safety level to reduce costs?

The design basis must be thoroughly addressed and be trackable.

For any project, the design basis must be thoroughly assessed so that all assumptions for the design and the operations are well established and can be tracked and discussed. This design basis must be available before the finalization of the conceptual engineering of the project.

6. Future concerns

The role of the engineering schools is vital.

From the viewpoint of the teachers, do we educate engineers to identify risk and robust engineering, or do we emphasize the use of large computer programs too much, which can immediately lead to technical problems if the input variables are incorrect or if the limitations of the programs are not properly understood?

The automated design.

This author is particularly concerned that a high level of trust in the use of AI for design purposes could lead to a new series of failures in the offshore and marine industry, when the knowledge base of the AI system cannot capture all potential loss scenarios, and when risk analysis is performed automatically.

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